

D5.2

Project website and blog

May 31, 2023

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Johannes Emmerling, CMCC	General revision	26/05/2023
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1 CAPABLE Website wireframe

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CLIMATE POLICY ACCEPTABILITY ECONOMIC FRAMEWORK

WELCOME TO CAPABLE

CAPABLE will provide robust, resilient and actionable recommendations for the design of socially and economically acceptable climate policy measures for 2030 and beyond.

[Read more](#) →

FIND OUT MORE ABOUT OUR OBJECTIVES IN THE ABOUT SECTION

9+

RESEARCHERS INVOLVED

An interdisciplinary team spanning across 7 European countries

3

INSTITUTIONS

Top European climate and policy research centers

200k

TOTALEU CONTRIBUTION

CAPABLE is financed under the Horizon Europe programme

3m

PROJECT DURATION

The project started on Jan 1 2023 and will last until Dec 31 2025

WHAT WE AIM TO

CAPABLE OBJECTIVES

[Read more](#) →

001

Addressing issues of deep uncertainty, social heterogeneity of actors, behavioural responses and biases, and multi-objective welfare measurement.

DEVELOP NEW METHODS FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DECISION-MAKING

002

Particularly on determinants of public support and opposition driving the political feasibility of climate policies.

ENHANCE THE EMPIRICAL KNOWLEDGE OF PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS OF CLIMATE POLICIES

003

With a focus on policy implementation and sequencing, and on policies of the Fit for 55 package – with the best available scientific evidence.

SYNTHESIZE THE RICH LITERATURE ON CLIMATE POLICY IMPACT EVALUATION

004

From the European and national levels to regional city levels, as well as recent citizen

ANALYSE THE ROLE OF POLICYMAKERS AT VARIOUS

To be disseminated, exploited, and facilitated by the development of an online policy evaluation tool.

DESIGN ACTIONABLE AND EFFECTIVE CLIMATE POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

OUR TEAM

A GROUP PICTURE OF THE CAPABLE TEAM AT THE END OF THE KICK-OFF WORKSHOP IN MILAN IN MARCH 2023

Feasibility . Acceptance . Efficiency . Feasibility . Acceptance . Efficiency . Feasibility . Acceptance . Efficiency . Fe

The governments' responses to the energy crisis was quick and robust but untargeted, and overall the crisis had not derailed much of the climate change mitigation efforts.

TOBIAS KRUSE
OECD

OUR TEAM

A WIDE VARIETY OF BACKGROUNDS

From social psychology and political science to economics and environmental sciences - each researcher brings a fundamental contribution to the mix.

JAMES TREMEWAN
WP1 RESEARCHER AT IESEG-CNRS

NIKLAS DÖBBELING
WP3 RESEARCHER AT MCC

LOIC BERGER
WP1 COORDINATOR AT IESEG-CNRS

JAN MINX
WP3 RESEARCHER AT MCC

OUR FIRST WEBINAR

IMPACT OF GREEN POLICIES ON LOCAL ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE

Watch video →

● Watch the video of our first webinar dedicated to the impact of the EU ETS on employment and competitiveness

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CAPABLE: *ClimAte Policy AcceptaBil.ity Economic framework* is a research project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101056891.

MOTIVATIONS

CAPABLE (*ClimAte Policy AcceptaBil.ity Economic framework*) is a research project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056891.

Overall, policies to transform the European economy to meet the global climate targets of the Paris agreement need to be cost-effective, fair, and politically and socially feasible.

However, many policies face a tension between ambition and **effectiveness** on the one hand and **social and political feasibility** on the other. Furthermore, climate policies often face low acceptance among the general public and business communities, partly due to the lack of scientific evidence on the socio-economic effectiveness and broader performance of climate policies.

There is therefore a **fundamental challenge for policy design** which requires robust scientific methods to assess policy portfolios and the “sequencing” of policies. CAPABLE is addressing these challenges by improving economic analysis in four ways:

1. utilize the existing evidence base, summarize it clearly and efficiently, and make it accessible and usable to policymakers;
2. develop frameworks for decision-making under deep uncertainty, taking into account behavioural factors and heterogeneous social actors;
3. account for the social acceptability and political feasibility of policies and their sequencing;
4. explicitly take into account preferences, knowledge and capabilities of policymakers as actors in the process.

The ambition of the CAPABLE project is to provide **methodological and empirical advances in policy evaluation by integrating economic and social sciences**.

CAPABLE will provide a thorough evaluation of climate policies by including social acceptability and policy heterogeneity and by considering the role of policymakers explicitly. CAPABLE will advance state-of-the-art decision-making by proposing **broader economic frameworks**. It will leverage the **interdisciplinary competences of the consortium** in economics, social psychology, political science and environmental science.

”
CAPABLE WILL PROVIDE ROBUST, RESILIENT AND ACTIONABLE RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE DESIGN OF SOCIALLY AND ECONOMICALLY ACCEPTABLE CLIMATE POLICY MEASURES FOR 2030 AND BEYOND.

The project will generate original empirical evidence through a variety of elicitation methods such as interviews, surveys and experimental economic approaches applied to various stakeholders (citizens, consumers, firms, policy-makers). Taken together, the methodological and empirical advancements will provide broader evidence for desirable climate strategies in Europe, along with lessons for the rest of the world. The methodological and empirical contributions will allow in-depth evaluations of existing as well as planned or foreseeable policies within the EU Green Deal.

Finally, we will integrate scientific evidence, an **interactive stakeholder dialogue**, and various dissemination channels, including a **new online policy evaluation tool** as a user-oriented service for climate policymakers at the EU, national, and local level.

OBJECTIVES AND AMBITIONS

The overall aim of CAPABLE is to develop and operationalize multi-objective decision making frameworks to help evaluate effective, yet socially and politically feasible, climate and environmental policies in Europe. This will be accomplished through five objectives:

1) DEVELOP NEW METHODS FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DECISION-MAKING -

Addressing issues of deep uncertainty, social heterogeneity of actors, behavioural responses and biases, and multi-objective welfare measurement.

Traditional approaches to policy design and evaluation tend to rely on classical theories that

1. do not distinguish between types of uncertainty (thus neglecting deep uncertainty)
2. use a "representative agent" (thereby ignoring issues of heterogeneity on e.g. income, gender, race)
3. take the ideal "social planner" perspective without giving due attention to the potential behavioural response by the general public
4. focus too narrowly on a trade-off between costs and benefits of a single issue instead of evaluating policies under multidimensional welfare criteria

CAPABLE offers methodological advancements in these four key dimensions.

2) ENHANCE THE EMPIRICAL KNOWLEDGE OF PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS OF CLIMATE POLICIES +

3) SYNTHESIZE THE RICH LITERATURE ON CLIMATE POLICY IMPACT EVALUATION +

4) ANALYSE THE ROLE OF POLICYMAKERS AT VARIOUS LEVELS +

5) DESIGN ACTIONABLE AND EFFECTIVE CLIMATE POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS +

WORKPLAN & WORKPACKAGES

The CAPABLE project is organized in six work packages, with **WP1 providing methodological advancements** and **WP2 focusing on the role of social and political feasibility**. Their insights inform the **policy evaluation of existing and planned policies** in the EU with a focus on the Fit for 55 package performed in **WP3**. Then, we will evaluate the crucial role of policymaking and political actors at the different levels from cities, local, national to supra-national and how policymakers and their **perception shapes policy outcomes and acceptability** in **WP4**. **WP5 provides bidirectional interactions with key stakeholders** through a continuous co-design approach with the key stakeholders in the advisory board and a larger set of policymakers and stakeholders, taking in both key input to the work packages and providing high-level findings, an online tool, and capacity building activities. **WP6 organizes the project management** of CAPABLE.

Workpackages organization and list of tasks

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056891 – CAPABLE – ClimAte Policy AcceptaBILity Economic framework.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

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THE RESEARCHERS

The CAPABLE team assembles more than 40 researchers from 11 different European research institutions in 7 countries

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The CAPABLE team assembles more than 40 researchers from 11 different European research institutions in 7 countries

Contact us [→](#)

THE INSTITUTIONS

The CAPABLE consortium is coordinated by the *European Institute on Economics and the Environment (RFF-CMCC)* and is composed by a total of 11 institutional partners located in 7 European countries. Click the logo or the acronyms below to visit our partners' institutional websites.

element6

1. European Institute on Economics and the Environment (RFF-CMCC) – ITALY
2. EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE (EUI) – ITALY
3. INSTITUT D'ÉCONOMIE SCIENTIFIQUE ET DE GESTION (IESEG) – FRANCE
4. CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE (CNRS) – FRANCE
5. POTSDAM INSTITUT FÜR KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG (PIK) – GERMANY
6. MERCATOR RESEARCH INSTITUTE ON GLOBAL COMMONS AND CLIMATE CHANGE (MCC) – GERMANY
7. UNIVERSITAT AUTÒNOMA DE BARCELONA (UAB) – SPAIN
8. UNIVERZITA KARLOVA (CUNI) – CZECH REPUBLIC
9. RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN (RUG) – THE NETHERLANDS
10. ELEMENTSIX DI JACOPO CRIMI (E6) – ITALY
11. EIDGENÖSSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH (ETH) – SWITZERLAND

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NEWS

16 May

NEWS
**IMPACT OF GREEN
POLICIES ON LOCAL
ECONOMIC
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Watch the video of our first webinar dedicated to the impact of the EU ETS on employment and competitiveness...

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3 Apr

NEWS
**D5.3: MINUTES AND
CONCLUSIONS OF THE
WORKSHOP 1**

Deliverable 5.3 contains the minutes and conclusions of the first CAPABLE policy workshop ...

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6 Mar

NEWS
CAPABLE KO MEETING

CAPABLE Kick-off meeting Held on February 28th & March 1st, 2023: RFF-CMCC European Institute on Economics and t

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Browse policies 27 May

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